

Design of growth-coupled measurements of histidine kinase function

A proposal for onboarding histidine kinases to the protein sequence-to-function measurement platform.

- Uses a gene circuit to tie successful ligand-dependent activation and subsequent interdomain signal transduction of histidine kinases to bacterial cell growth
- Calibration variants span the dynamic range of activity enable quantitative function measurements
- First dataset collection will focus on measuring variants of a native *E. coli* histidine kinase, CpxA, re-engineered to have its native sensor domain replaced with a fully de novo, minimal metal-binding sensor domain

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Contributors

Align to Innovate:

Peter Kelly - Program Director, Open Datasets Initiative

Dana Cortade - Technical Project Manager, Open Datasets Initiative

Proposal Co-Leaders:

Katie Hatstat - PhD, Postdoctoral Fellow, DeGrado Lab, UCSF

Prof. Bill DeGrado - Professor, Dept. of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, UCSF

David Ross, PhD - Living Measurement Systems Foundry, National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST)

Reviewers:

Gabriel J. Rocklin - Professor, Department of Pharmacology, Northwestern University,

Ivan Korendovych - Professor, Biochemistry, Baylor University

Kimberly A. Reynolds - Associate Professor, Lyda Hill Department of Bioinformatics, The University of Texas Southwestern Medical Center

W. Seth Childers - Associate Professor, Department of Chemistry, University of Pittsburgh

Prabha Ramakrishnan - PhD, Director, Business Development, Ginkgo Bioworks

Overview

Bacteria employ signaling proteins like bacterial histidine kinases (HKs) to sense environmental stimuli and initiate a transcriptional response through a series of conformational changes and enzymatic steps. Despite the prevalence of these receptors, we still lack significant understanding of how specific signals are detected and propagated through the protein scaffold to induce switch-like behavior with finely tuned specificity, sensitivity, and transcriptional output. Generating large-scale HK genotype-phenotype relationships will enable us to parse out allosteric networks that enable and regulate intramolecular signal transduction, providing molecular insights into the complex mechanisms by which these organisms sense and adapt to their environment.

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Context, Significance, and Impact

Biological system and motivation:

Transmembrane signaling is a ubiquitous and essential biological process, cell-environment and cell-cell interactions. Transmembrane receptors must exhibit finely tuned specificity and selectivity, converting an external stimulus (input) into an intracellular response (output) of a desired magnitude and in the right time and place. This can occur through receptor clustering, conformational changes within a single domain, or signaling that occurs through multiple subdomains within a pre-assembled complex. In the latter case, allosteric signaling requires that a stimulus triggers only a small change at the input domain that is then amplified down the receptor to mediate the output.

Histidine kinases rely on interdomain signal transduction to enable bacteria, plants, and fungi to sense and adapt to their environment. Part of two-component systems, HKs detect extracellular ligands or environmental stimuli, which initiate an intramolecular signal transduction cascade to initiate a phospho-relay in which HKs first auto-phosphorylate then trans-phosphorylate a cognate response regulator, which acts as a transcription factor to control genetic responses (Figure 1).¹⁻⁵ These systems are critical in allowing bacteria to sense and respond to their environment and are often involved in growth and pathogenicity. Importantly, the specificity, sensitivity, and output of two-component systems has

to be finely tuned and tightly regulated such that the bacteria can properly sense and adapt to environmental signals.

Despite the prevalence of these receptors, we still lack significant understanding of how specific signals are detected and propagated through the protein scaffold to induce switch-like behavior with finely tuned specificity, sensitivity, and output. Generating large-scale HK genotype-phenotype relationships will enable us to parse out allosteric networks that enable intramolecular signal transduction and identify determinants of signaling specificity and output, providing molecular insights into the complex mechanisms by which these organisms sense and adapt to their environment. *Specifically, we ask: 1) how do changes in individual subdomains (alone and in combination) alter overall signaling profiles? 2) Do receptors that sense multiple stimuli rely on the same allosteric signaling pathways? And 3) is the modularity of these receptors predictable and engineerable?* Mechanistic insight into these sequence-function relationships will inform our understanding of how Nature has tuned these signaling systems and will advance our understanding of how signals are propagated through multiple modular subdomains. This will in turn enable future design and engineering of precisely tuned signaling systems with user-defined specificity, a long-standing goal in protein design and synthetic biology.

Motivation for adapting a growth-based assay and experimental considerations:

Current efforts toward elucidating signal transduction mechanisms in HKs rely on a combination of structural (X-ray crystallography)⁶⁻⁹ and biochemical techniques (cysteine-scanning coupled with reporter assays, alanine scanning, etc.)¹⁰⁻¹² to identify conformational rearrangements that occur during a signaling event. However, there are no full-length structures of any transmembrane histidine kinase to date, and the traditional biochemical approaches are laborious and low-throughput, with very few high-throughput analyses reported thus far. A fitness-based screening platform has also not yet been, to our knowledge, implemented to measure HK sequence-function relationships, with most reporter assays relying on a coupled colorimetric (e.g. b-galactosidase) or fluorescent readout and few studies conducted in high-throughput to date.¹³⁻¹⁷ Therefore, we propose adaptation of the fitness assay to quantify genotype-phenotype landscapes of prototypical HKs in high-throughput.

We propose to employ high-throughput, quantitative measurements to understand the relationship between individual subdomains within an HK during a signal transduction event. Here, we consider a thermodynamic model of signaling,^{11,16,18} where a signal transduction event can be considered not just as a series of geometric/conformational rearrangements that are propagated down the HK scaffold but as a series of energetically coupled transitions. In this model, ligand binding induces a thermodynamic shift at the sensor domain, which subsequently shifts the thermodynamic equilibrium of each coupled domain downstream to switch kinase activity state. This model treats signaling (and the HKs themselves) as highly modular, where the

Figure 1: Schematic of a two-component system, which consists of a histidine kinase (HK) and cognate response regulator (RR).

specific identity of the subdomain should not matter as long as the thermodynamic shift and coupling is sufficient for the signal to be propagated through the series of subdomains. This idea is supported by efforts toward engineering HK chimeras,^{19–25} where signaling is retained upon domain shuffling with subdomains from other HKs, and in HK evolution,³ where diversity is thought to arise through gene transfer and shuffling events. Because of the intrinsic modularity of this signaling system, the high-throughput fitness assay will allow us to generate libraries of natural HK mutants or HK chimeras and introduce diversity within and across subdomains in a combinatorial manner to understand how variation in different subdomains alters signal transduction.

Because there is not an established record of screening HK variants in pooled fitness assays, we propose to calibrate and tune the assay with prototypical HKs from *E. coli* because 1) they have been sufficiently well-studied to provide to establish calibration libraries and 2) *E. coli* has been previously established as a suitable host organism for the fitness assay platform. Importantly, the proposed target HKs detects multiple ligands/stimuli, providing an opportunity to screen the variant libraries in the presence of multiple ligands to determine if the HK employs ligand-dependent signaling mechanisms or allosteric networks. Because the HK is part of the two-component system, variations will be introduced into the HK (gene of interest), while the response regulator and reporter promoter will be held constant (action site). We plan to focus mutations on the domains upstream of the catalytic region, which comprises the dimerization and histidine phosphotransfer (DHp) domain and autokinase domain. This will focus mutations on the regions that regulate sensing and signal transduction and eliminate confounding variables introduced by mutations in the region that dictates RR recognition (in the DHp domain) or catalytic activity (autokinase domain). This will allow us

to specifically study the mechanism of signal transduction within the HK itself. The calibration library will be generated based on previous mechanistic studies from our lab and others, and the pilot and large-scale libraries will be designed with a combination of rational and random mutations throughout the HK scaffold.

The pooled fitness assay will enable us to generate quantitative dose response curves for many variants in a single assay run. As many HKs exhibit both kinase and phosphatase activities (where the kinase state turns “on” the downstream signal by phosphorylating the cognate RR, and phosphatase activity dictates the “off” state of the system by dephosphorylating the RR), we will treat the dose response activity as a net readout of both states. Based on prior knowledge of the equilibrium between these opposing states,²⁶ we can model the effect of changes in kinase and/or phosphatase activity and use this information to help us identify which changes in dose-response profiles may result from changes in kinase versus phosphatase activity.^{12,27,28} Then, we can validate mutants with changes in dose-response profiles in a targeted manner to directly assess changes in kinase/phosphatase activities.^{29,30}

Outlook:

We anticipate that the datasets generated from this effort will allow us to identify, predict, and design signal transduction networks with defined specificity and output. In particular, the pilot- and large-scale datasets will allow us to build predictive models to understand how variation in sequence in different regions of the HK affect overall signal transduction profiles. This effort will allow us to establish principles that define signal transduction which will inform future design of fully *de novo*, orthogonal signaling systems, a longstanding challenge in protein design and synthetic biology.

Gene of Interest (GOI) Region

The gene of interest region contains an operon with the protein sequence to be expressed in the opposite orientation to the genes in the circuit region (Figure 2). This prevents unintended expression of genes in the circuit. It also contains barcode region homology and circuit region homology for ease of cloning. In this platform, the GOI is the HK (or respective variant). While we have HK expression/reporter plasmids established in the DeGrado lab from previous projects, the construction of the plasmid varies from the format used in previous Align to Innovate efforts. If we follow the proposed template, the GOI region will be as follows:

In this GOI region, expression of the histidine kinase is under control of an inducible promoter (pTrc promoter in previous HK reporter constructs, regulated by the LacI transcription factor

from the host cell genome), and expression will be tuned via [inducer], promoter, and the ribosome binding site (RBS). This is a critical component of developing and tuning the assay as *E. coli* can be sensitive to HK overexpression, and a systematic method to optimizing GOI expression has been established in other projects that employ the pooled growth assay approach (see Align-to-Innovate transcription factor project). The HK expression region is in the opposite direction on the plasmid of the reporter sequence and is flanked by terminators to ensure that only the desired region is transcribed and translated. Barcodes will be included outside of the transcribed region, and the full region is flanked by homology arms for cloning into the full GOI/reporter plasmid.

Selection Cassette

The selection cassette is a region of the plasmid that is specific to each function (Fig. A9). For the two-component systems, the action site is a promoter that is responsive to the HK/RR pair of interest. In our system, the GOI will be expressed via the plasmid system described below, and the cognate response regulator is endogenously expressed in *E. coli*. Ligand-dependent activation of the HK will initiate a phospho-relay in which the HK first auto-phosphorylates and then trans-phosphorylates its cognate response regulator (RR). The phosphorylated RR will then act as a transcription factor, regulating expression of the reporter in the selection cassette. The promoter in our selection cassette will control expression of an antibiotic resistance gene (Ab^R) for fitness assays and a fluorescent reporter for function assays. We will initially express

both in tandem on the same plasmid as the GOI for development and tuning but may modify to express just the selection gene for fitness assays after assay tuning. The promoter will be chosen based on previously established reporter assays from the lab in which we have engineered reporter systems using promoters from the native HK/RR regulon (Figure 3). Both the promoter and RBS can be tuned to modify output of the reporter system during assay development. If necessary, the cognate response regulator can be co-over-expressed on a second plasmid to boost signal from the two-component system. However, we would like to avoid using a dual plasmid system if possible. If needed, the RR can also be re-engineered via domain shuffling of the DNA-binding domain to eliminate cross-regulation at the promoter level or further tune signaling output.³¹

Proposed Hosts and Plasmids

The HKs of interest for assay development are *E. coli* proteins (or engineered from *E. coli* proteins), and we have several established strains (derived from MG1655) with the native HK knocked out to avoid endogenous cross-talk with the variant and reporter system.^{10,11,16,32,33} While HKs are widely conserved and found in bacteria, plants, and fungi, establishing our mechanistic understanding in an easily culturable and robust bacterial strain provides a more facile experimental system.

We propose starting with trimethoprim (resistance gene: DHFR variant not susceptible to trimethoprim; in development in other

projects at NIST) selection initially as the dynamic range of one of the target HKs for tuning has been shown to be fairly low; thus, we anticipate that using zeocin or trimethoprim resistance will give us more sensitivity in the assay tuning. The promoter for HK-dependent reporter expression will be chosen based on previously used promoter/reporter constructs from our lab, but promoters can be swapped with other promoters from the HK/RR regulon as necessary to tune reporter output.

Link to Benchling for previously established HK reporter plasmid:

[LINK](#)

Link to Benchling for proposed HK reporter plasmid following Align to innovate construct design:

[LINK](#)

Proposed Protein Targets

Because a high-throughput fitness assay has not been previously applied to study HK signal transduction, we propose to conduct initial assay development and pilot-scale datasets with variants of well-studied HKs in their native organism, *E. coli*, which has already been implemented as a host in high-throughput fitness assays through this initiative. Then, we propose to

Assay development and tuning:

For assay development, we propose to generate a targeted genotype-phenotype dataset for several native and engineered HKs as proof-of-concept to validate that HK activity can be quantitatively measured using both function and fitness assays. For assay development, HKs with varied signaling profiles and specificities (ligands, dynamic range, basal activity) will be used for tuning the assay system to ensure that tuning is performed in a generalizable manner to enable future use of the assay with diverse HKs.

Pilot scale:

In the pilot-scale assay, we propose to build a variant library of an engineered HK chimera that we have previously developed. We previously tested if our mechanistic understanding of signaling in multidomain, energetically coupled systems has progressed sufficiently to enable *de novo* design of a functional sensor domain. Specifically, we sought to test our understanding of the role of ligand binding, conformational dynamics, and coupling to downstream domains in mediating signaling profiles. We demonstrated that HK signaling can be re-wired using a *de novo* designed, metal-binding sensor domain and that signaling output varies as properties of the sensor domain and the linker between sensor and downstream domain are varied. This supports our thermodynamic signaling model and builds upon the inherent modularity of the HK scaffold. We have interest in expanding sensor domain design to other ligands, but first seek to establish biophysical parameters that can inform future design of HK chimera. We aim to further this effort by targeting

mutations to key regions of the HK combinatorially to both 1) evolve the specificity of the HK toward other metals and 2) quantify the effect of variation in specific subdomains and linkers between them (alone and in combination) on signaling output. This data (and subsequent ML models trained on the dataset) will provide insight into the features that govern the specificity and sensitivity of multidomain, intramolecular signal transduction and inform rational engineering and *de novo* design of orthogonal signaling systems.

Large scale:

Following assay development and pilot-scale experiments, we propose to further explore specific mechanistic questions about interdomain signaling in these modular receptors, including: 1) *Does sequence predictably encode switch behavior?* 2) *Do receptors that sense multiple stimuli rely on the same allosteric signaling pathways?* And 3) *is the modularity of these receptors predictable and engineerable?* For the first two questions, mutational scanning can provide sequence-function relationships that reveal critical features controlling substrate specificity and the on/off switch that regulates kinase activity state. Regarding modularity, large chimera libraries can be generated through combinatorial domain shuffling to quantitatively characterize the inherent modularity of the HK scaffold and determine the effect of varying subdomain identity on signaling output. Here, we propose to generate chimera libraries where subdomains are selected that represent major fold families (e.g. for sensor domain: PAS, Cache, GAF, Chase; for linker domain: HAMP, PAS, GAF) and to vary the linkers between subdomains to establish parameters regarding domain identity and linker length that will inform future design of chimeric receptors. In either case, the datasets can be designed to be comprehensive but not exhaustive, providing training sets for predictive models that can identify function-determining features and enable design and engineering of precisely tuned signaling systems with controlled specificity and output.

Figure 4: Selection strategy for choosing targets.

Proposed Controls for Assay Development

Stage 1 – Development and Tuning

For the two-component systems, the GOI sequence is the HK (which will be varied), while the action site is its cognate response regulator + promoter pair (which will be held constant, though the promoter can be varied as needed for tuning of the system).

Initial candidate sequences will be cloned into the Align to Innovate plasmid construct which will be modified to replace the reporter promoter with a HK/RR responsive promoter, or a previously established HK reporter plasmid will be modified to incorporate a barcode region. Cloned constructs will be confirmed by whole plasmid sequencing and will be validated in previously established *E. coli* knockout strains (derived from MG1655). In parallel, we will screen activity using previously established reporter assays (genetically incorporated reporter) to make sure that the activity and sensitivity to ligand we observe in the Align to Innovate plasmid construct is consistent with our previous studies.

Using CpxA and PhoQ as initial HK candidates provides two advantages: the HKs exhibit similar overall architectures (sensor-transmembrane-HAMP-DHp-autokinase domains) but have different basal activity (PhoQ basal state = kinase on; CpxA basal state = kinase off) and different dynamic ranges upon induction. This will allow us to tune the reporter system accordingly to ensure that we can reliably capture the activity of HKs with different basal and inducible activity. It will also help to establish if the fitness assay is generalizable to HKs with different signaling profiles.

It is important to note that PhoQ is proposed as an initial candidate because we have more sequence-function data for PhoQ relative to other prototypical HKs;^{10,11,32,34,35} however, it is a regulator of many cellular processes.³⁶ Thus mutation of PhoQ may have an effect on basal fitness of the cells independent of selective pressure in the fitness assay. We will screen cell

viability of established PhoQ mutants in a $\Delta phoQ$ strain before using PhoQ to tune the assay to ensure that there are no confounding effects on viability from introduction of PhoQ mutants. If PhoQ mutants prove deleterious to overall cell viability in the absence of selective pressure, we can use other HKs for tuning that have established and convenient input and some established sequence-function information (like NarX, a nitrate sensor with a more complex cytoplasmic architecture³⁷ or TtrS, a tetrathionate sensor that has been previously protected into *E. coli*^{24,27}).

In the initial tuning phase, as needed, constructs will be cloned for each HK that contain 2-3 different HK/RR-dependent promoters (of varied strengths) and 2 RBS sequences in all combinations (6 reporter region variants per HK).

Initial tuning will be conducted using fluorescence reporter readout (measured via flow cytometry).

1. Following the Singleplex Assay for Function Measurements protocol³⁸, we will screen HK activity via fluorescence reporter using flow cytometry. Initial screening will be conducted at UCSF using an Attune NxT flow cytometer (available through the UCSF Laboratory for Cell Analysis Cytometry Core Facility). Plates will be set up with three replicates per HK and a gradient of ligand (Mg²⁺ and Ca²⁺ for PhoQ, and brilacidin for CpxA).

NOTE: A consideration for this stage of optimization is that the ligands for PhoQ and CpxA may have an effect on overall growth rate or viability of the bacterial cultures (independent of the selection pressure in the fitness assay). Control experiments will be performed in which cell viability and growth with varied [ligand] will be monitored to determine if additional normalization steps are required to account for any ligand-dependent changes in cell viability.

2. Following the Singleplex Assay for Function experiment, the Singleplex Assay for Fitness Measurements protocol³⁹ will be followed to assess the fitness of each HK as a function of inducer concentration. We propose to start with trimethoprim selection (resistance gene: DHFR variant not susceptible to trimethoprim) as we anticipate that it will provide greater sensitivity for HKs or variants with low dynamic range. The fitness assay will be conducted with a 2D gradient of [ligand] and [antibiotic] with different antibiotic concentrations in each column and different inducer concentration in each row. Both concentration gradients will have a 2-fold difference between adjacent wells. The maximum trimethoprim concentration will be determined from previous data with trimethoprim selection in transcription factor libraries. The maximum inducer concentration will be chosen (using the data from the function measurement in the previous step) to optimally span the range of available functions. Two replicates will be measured, one on each half of the plate.

Action site (RR + promoter)	HK (GOI)	Ligand	Expected activity
PhoP + pMgtA promoter	PhoQ-WT	Mg ²⁺ , Ca ²⁺	Narrow dynamic range Variable with [Mg ²⁺], [Ca ²⁺], pH, or [NaCl] On to off switch (on in low divalent cation, off with high divalent cation)
CpxR + pCpxP promoter	CpxA-WT	brilacidin	Broad dynamic range Variable with [brilacidin], a peptidomimetic drug Off to on switch (off in absence of ligand, on in presence of ligand)

Table 1: HK and response regulator/promoter pairs that will be used for assay development.

Stage 2 – Normalization and Calibration Controls

Two sets of normalization and calibration experiments will be performed, one with PhoQ (Table B2) and one with CpxA (Table B3). For each, a promoter has been proposed that has previously been used for fluorescent or enzyme-coupled colorimetric reporter assays; as needed, other promoters from the HK/RR regulon can be swapped in for tuning in Stage 1 and the optimized operator will be carried forward to Stage 2 accordingly.

For CpxA and PhoQ, mutations/insertions have been identified from previously reported functional assays that shift the dynamic range or sensitivity of the HK. In each set of mutants, at least one variant has been shown to display a constitutively active (“always on” or signal-blind) profile and will serve as a normalization control.

An additional normalization control will also be used, with a simple constitutive promoter controlling expression of the trimethoprim resistance gene. This control is expected to be useful in disentangling fitness effects and global changes in translation resulting from changes in the concentration of Mg²⁺ and other cations that are important for cell metabolism.

Singleplex fitness assay with normalization controls:

For the fitness measurement of the normalization sequences for the HK dataset, the plate layout will be designed with two trimethoprim concentration gradients, one to be measured with

a high concentration of ligand Mg²⁺/Ca²⁺ for PhoQ, brilacidin/ Zn²⁺ for CpxA and CpxA chimeras), and the other without ligand. The two gradients will be pipetted in opposite directions to reduce effects from differences in position within the plate. For samples with ligands, the same concentration will be used in all wells and concentrations will be determined from Stage 1 experiments.

Quantification of protein expression levels:

As necessary, we will conduct a secondary set of assays/screens to determine if the changes in fitness result solely from changes in signal transduction or if mutations change the level of HK expression. For normalization and calibration (with limited mutants in the library), this could be done with western blotting. However, this is not scalable for the large pooled assay. Here, we propose to employ an abundance protein fragment complementation assay as a secondary screen as necessary where the variants will be expressed in fusion with a fragment of DHFR in the presence of high levels of the other DHFR fragment⁴¹. In this assay, fitness is a function of protein expression levels. Thus, we can use this data as a normalization to account for changes in activity versus expression. While this involves an additional cloning and screening step, it avoids other abundance quantification methods like fluorescent protein fusions that may interfere with HK activity.

Operator (action site)	HK (GOI)	Ligand	Expected activity	Type of Control	Reference
PhoP + mgtB promoter	PhoQ-D179L	Mg ²⁺ , Ca ²⁺	Constitutively active	Normalization	34
PhoP + mgtB promoter	PhoQ-N202A	Mg ²⁺ , Ca ²⁺	Constitutively inactive	Normalization	32
Constitutive promoter	N/A	N/A	High constitutive activity of AbR	Normalization	N/A
PhoP + mgtB promoter	PhoQ-WT	Mg ²⁺ , Ca ²⁺	On (low divalent cation) to off (high divalent cation)	Calibration	35
PhoP + mgtB promoter	PhoQ-T48Y	Mg ²⁺ , Ca ²⁺	Greater dynamic range than WT	Calibration	35
PhoP + mgtB promoter	PhoQ-T48F	Mg ²⁺ , Ca ²⁺	Signal blind to Ca ²⁺ , but still sensitive to Mg ²⁺	Calibration	35
PhoP + mgtB promoter	PhoQ-T48K	Mg ²⁺ , Ca ²⁺	Lower dynamic range than WT	Calibration	35

Table 2: PhoQ variants and RR/promoter action sites for normalization and calibration experiments.

Operator (action site)	HK (GOI)	Ligand	Expected activity	Type of Control	Reference
CpxP + cpxP promoter	CpxA with Gly7 insertion	brilacidin	Constitutively high	Normalization	11
CpxP + cpxP promoter	CpxA-Y123A	brilacidin	Constitutively overactive	Normalization	40
CpxP + cpxP promoter	CpxA-WT	brilacidin	Off (low brilacidin) to on (high brilacidin)	Calibration	11
CpxP + cpxP promoter	CpxA-N107D	brilacidin	Constitutively overactive	Calibration	40
CpxP + cpxP promoter	CpxA-Zinc chimera v1-K29/L160	Zn ²⁺	Constitutively active	Normalization	Hatstat et al., unpublished
CpxP + cpxP promoter	CpxA-Zinc chimera v1-R33/L160	Zn ²⁺	Low basal activity + narrow dynamic range	Calibration	Hatstat et al., unpublished
CpxP + cpxP promoter	CpxA-Zinc chimera v2-K29/L160	Zn ²⁺	High basal activity + narrow dynamic range	Calibration	Hatstat et al., unpublished
CpxP + cpxP promoter	CpxA-Zinc chimera v2-L30/F156	Zn ²⁺	Low basal activity + large dynamic range	Calibration	Hatstat et al., unpublished

Table 3: CpxA variants and RR/promoter action sites for normalization and calibration experiments.

Pilot-Scale Collection

For the pilot-scale assay, we aim to expand our thermodynamic coupling hypothesis of signaling by looking at the effects of mutation within and across subdomains in a combinatorial manner. To do so, we will build upon a previous HK chimera engineering effort in which we demonstrated that an *E. coli* HK, CpxA (used in assay tuning), could be successfully re-engineered by replacing its native sensor domain with a fully *de novo*, minimal metal-binding sensor domain. In this effort, we demonstrated that variation of the sensor domain properties and the linker length between the sensor domain and the rest of the HK scaffold affect signaling output (Hatstat et al., in preparation). Here, we propose a combinatorial mutagenesis campaign in which mutations are introduced into discrete subdomains of the engineered chimera to understand the effect of varying subdomain properties individually and combinatorially. We will focus mutations in the sensor domain and linker (HAMP) domain, and avoid mutations in regions that have been previously established to affect dimerization, RR recognition, or catalysis. We also propose to exclude mutations

to the transmembrane domain initially as previous work from our lab has shown that modification of a single polar residue in this region can completely ablate signaling.³² Thus, we anticipate it to be less susceptible to variation. Single and multiple mutants dispersed throughout these regions alone and in combination will be sufficient to generate a library of the desired scale (~100,000 HK variants). By targeting mutations to discrete subdomains, we can quantitatively measure the relationship between subdomains and properties thereof. We will also vary the metal binding site residues in the sensor domain to allow us to explore the effect of metal chelation geometry and metal specificity on signaling output, and we will vary the linker sequence between the sensor and transmembrane domains to understand how linker rigidity affects signaling output. This approach provides a variety of parameters in the data set (metal ligand, chelation residues/geometry, mutation(s), linker sequence, signaling output) that will be used to train a predictive model for understanding the molecular determinants of signaling.

Large-Scale Collection

Moving beyond the pilot-scale measurement, we envision numerous routes to help us quantify and design molecular determinants of signal transduction in the two component system. We seek to answer mechanistic questions including:

1) How does sequence encode switch behavior, and is it predictable? 2) Do receptors that sense multiple stimuli rely on the same allosteric signaling pathways?

- Here, we propose to screen mutagenesis libraries for many natural HKs in parallel to identify ligand-specific allosteric networks and mechanisms of tuning signal transduction outputs
 - We anticipate that spread out, low diversity (rational or through epPCR, affording variants with single and multiple mutations) instead of deep mutational scanning will be advantageous in generating a dataset that can be used to train predictive models and inform engineering of HK variants with precisely tuned signaling profiles
 - HKs with tractable, well-established ligands will be prioritized (small molecules/metabolites, ions, etc.), with HKs that respond to multiple stimuli being highest priority to address question #2

3) Is the modularity of these receptors predictable and engineerable?

- Here, we propose to generate chimera libraries where many chimeric HKs are assembled via domain shuffling from a library of modular “parts” (e.g. individual HK subdomains) to explore evolutionary mechanisms of HK specificity and output to establish parameters regarding domain identity and linker length that will inform future design of chimeric receptors
 - Subdomains will be selected that represent major fold families (e.g. for sensor domain: PAS, Cache, GAF, Chase; for linker domain: HAMP, PAS, GAF)
 - We propose to vary the linkers between subdomains as previous chimera engineering efforts have indicated that signaling is sensitive to length of the coiled-coil linker between subdomains
- Chimera libraries of fully *de novo* subdomains to establish first principles that govern the design of stimuli-responsive, switchable signal transduction systems

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